

Evolving Community Living Labs through Dual Safety Knowledge Circulation Systems to Prevent Injuries in Children

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Abstract

The prevention of choking and suffocation in children is an important global health issue. In the present study, we integrated the living lab approach into the community-based participatory research (CBPR) approach to co-design a new tool for the prevention of choking on cherry tomatoes. First, we present an overview of Love & Safety Omura, a community-based participatory living lab focused on the prevention of childhood injuries and introduce the dual Safety Knowledge Circulation systems. Then, we discuss how we designed our new tool for slicing cherry tomatoes in the Omura living lab. As a result of our study, we demonstrate the effectiveness of integrating a living lab into the CBPR approach that allows community members to define a problem in their own community, to explore innovative solutions, and to create a pathway for a safer community.

Keywords: *injury prevention, community-based participatory research, safety knowledge circulation system, health education*

1 Introduction

Suffocation caused by foreign-body airway obstruction is a leading cause of death in children around the world. Children explore the world using hand-to-mouth behavior, which contributes to an increased risk of injury (Gregori, 2008). The estimated number of choking and suffocation incidents per year among children under the age of 14 years is about 50,000 in the EU (n.d.) and 12,500 in the US (Chapin, 2013), with children aged 0–3 years at the greatest risk. In Japan from 2012 to 2016, 5901 children under the age of 5 years were treated for choking in emergency rooms in Tokyo alone (Tokyo Fire Department, n.d.), which suggests that around 60,000 incidents per year occur at the national level. Therefore, the prevention of choking and suffocation in children is an important health issue. According to Safe Kids Worldwide (n.d.), almost 60% of nonfatal choking incidents are food-related; therefore, as a preventive measure, they recommend cutting food into small pieces. Although cherry tomatoes are one of the causes of choking in children, many parents lack awareness of this risk. Therefore, the present study focused on the prevention of such incidents involving cherry tomatoes.

In the past 20 years or so, living lab research has played a critical role in fostering numerous innovations (Coorevits, 2017; Gascó, 2017; Leminen, 2017; Schuurman, 2017). More recently, the living lab approach has been applied to not only the design of new products and services, but also solutions to global health issues. Brankaert and den Ouden (2017) conducted living lab research to evaluate the effectiveness of a new device for dementia care. They concluded that a design-driven living lab was an effective method to explore innovative solutions with a deeper understanding of prototypes.

Calyam et al. (2017) used a living lab approach and experience principles to develop a cloud-based app for assessing health status among the elderly. Ahmad et al. (2016) identified social and individual factors to create a more inclusive mall environment for people with limitations in activities of daily living. These research findings highlight some examples of ways to achieve sustainable development goals in innovative ways.

From the public health perspective, especially in the field of health education, living lab and public health approaches share many common characteristics. Schuurman and Tõnurist (2017) defined living labs as “an organized approach to innovation consisting of real-life experimentation and active user involvement by means of different methods involving multiple stakeholders, as is implied in public-private-people character of living labs.” Their focus was user-centered co-creation and real-life contexts that emphasized user involvement while developing new innovations in terms of products, services, technologies, and experiences. In the field of public health, the community-based participatory research (CBPR) approach has been widely used to achieve health equity (Minkler, 2004; Wallerstein, 2010). CBPR focuses on community engagement in all phases of the research process, from defining a problem to finding a solution, as well as equal participation and partnerships and social action (Israel, 2001). The most important aspect of CBPR is the power distribution between the

“researchers” and the “researched” (Minkler, 2004). Implementation science, an emerging field in public health, clinical research, and education, deals with implementation problems in real-world settings to identify all aspects of implementation (what, why, who, and how) by involving multiple stakeholders (Ogden, 2014; Peters, 2013). Fundamentally, in living labs, CBPR, and implementation science, the key to reaching a goal is to share powers, including the knowledge, skills, and life experiences possessed by all stakeholders, and co-create a new innovation ecosystem.

Compared with the nature of engineering innovation, public health research is very much focused on finding solutions for specific health issues, but is not very focused on co-creating innovative technology-based solutions. Therefore, in the present study, we integrated the living lab approach into CBPR to co-design a new tool for the prevention of choking on cherry tomatoes. First, we present an overview of Love & Safety Omura, a community-based participatory living lab focused on the prevention of childhood injuries. Next, we share results from a survey on choking incidents involving cherry tomatoes and discuss the design of *Hitokuchi cut*, our new tool for slicing cherry tomatoes. Then, we discuss methodology for transforming community’s health issues into sustainable solutions from the viewpoint of transformative dimensions in the discussion section of this paper. Finally, we discuss practical implications of this new tool for the prevention of choking incidents.

Overview of Love & Safety Omura

Love & Safety Omura is a CBPR project that employs a living lab approach (Deguchi, 2012). It was started in 2008 and officially launched in 2011. In this living lab project, we collaborate with medical institutions, the local school board, day-care centers and kindergartens, and the police and fire departments in Omura, Nagasaki Prefecture, Japan. The purpose of this project is to create a multidisciplinary society where community members, educators, engineers, manufacturers and policy makers work together and recognize each other’s strengths. The project has two important characteristics. First, the drivers of this living lab are community members. The research topics are chosen based on their ideas and concerns, taking the results of injury data analysis into account. Second, the project is run by dual safety knowledge circulation (SKC) systems (Figure 1). Community members of SKC systems for Love & Safety Omura participate in living lab activities by providing knowledge and injury data from their own viewpoints. Community members of SKC systems for Kids’ Design Community participate in living lab activities by analyzing injury data, evaluating risks, and revising safety standards. The safety knowledge created in each system is circulated and shared with other systems. To date, we have circulated knowledge regarding bicycle, school, and button battery safety, as well as injury prevention from the viewpoint of teachers.

Figure 1: Dual safety knowledge circulation

Development of *Hitokuchi* cut

As mentioned above, we regularly analyzed localized injury data to assess problems in the community. Although the number of reported cases was small, choking and suffocation incidents were a top concern among community members. Therefore, the leader of Love & Safety Omura, a pediatrician in Omura city, issued a call to action to prevent choking incidents in children. Her particular concern was on cherry tomatoes because although children are frequently exposed to cherry tomatoes, most parents are unaware of their potential choking risk. The results of a survey we conducted on 31 community representatives, most of whom had small children in their households, indicated that 16 respondents (52%) did not know that cherry tomatoes could cause choking in children. None of the respondents had experienced any choking incidents involving cherry tomatoes, but eight had been scared because of similar food choking incidents involving grapes, bread, *ramune* (marble soda) and other hard candies, and gum.

After deciding to focus on choking incidents involving cherry tomatoes, we began working with designers from the Japan Industrial Designers' Association, the sole national organization for industrial designers in Japan, to develop a new tool for slicing cherry tomatoes. At this moment, most people use a knife to slice cherry tomatoes, which is too much bother to do. Therefore, we asked the designers to develop an attractive and easy-to-use tool especially for people who have small children. After devising 10 different types of tomato slicing tools, four were chosen for inclusion in the study at the end of the design stage; these four prototypes are shown in Figure 2. Prototype A is shaped like a castanet, and its concept is "fun to cut". Children would be the main users of this type. Prototype B is shaped

like tongs, and can be used it to cut something round. Prototype C is shaped like (small) scissors, and can be used to cut tomatoes on a plate. Prototype D is shaped like (large) scissors, and was designed for use at a salad bar in a restaurant. These new cherry tomato-slicing tools were named *Hitokuchi* cut (*hitokuchi* means “one bite”).

Figure 2: *Hitokuchi* cut prototypes

2 Introduction of *Hitokuchi* cut to the Omura community

On March 19, 2017, we presented *Hitokuchi* cut at the Love & Safety Festival 2017. This festival is held every year, and most families who live in Omura city and have a kindergarten-aged child participate in the event because it includes a children’s dance contest. Children dance to the music of “Let me know, ABUNAIKAMO”, which is the national theme song for a child injury prevention project created by the Consumer Affairs Agency. ABUNAIKAMO (*abunai* means “dangerous” and *kamo* means “duck”, as well as “maybe”) is a mascot character (Figure 3). A video showing the ABUNAIKAMO Dance Contest 2018 can be viewed online (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nWCtpGyltTE>).

Figure 3: The mascot character ABUNAIKAMO (source: <http://www.caa.go.jp/kodomo/symbol/index.php>)

The main focus of this study was not only to obtain feedback for developed tools, but also to educate community members on the choking risk associated with cherry tomatoes. We provided approximately 500 pieces of cherry tomatoes at the event site and asked participants at the festival to try and cut them using the four *Hitokuchi* cut prototypes. We also conducted a focus group to evaluate the usefulness of the tools. A photograph of the group activities is shown in Figure 4. During the focus group, we asked the participants about the size of each prototype, the level of ease in regard to cutting (6-point Likert scale, with 6 = the easiest and 1 = the most difficult), price, preference, actual scenarios in which they would want to use the tools, and points for improvement.

Figure 4. Photograph showing the focus group discussion

3 Evaluation of *Hitokuchi* cut

In total, 31 community members (five men, 26 women) participated in the focus group. When asked about the size of each prototype, most of the participants replied that the sizes of all four prototypes were just about right; however, six said that Prototype C was too small and nine said that Prototype D was too big. Regarding the level of ease in regard to cutting, the mean scores for Prototypes A, B, C, and D were 4.53, 3.87, 4.16, and 5.13, respectively. When asked what price they would be willing to pay for the tools, 20 participants said, “less than 500 yen (about 3.85 euro) and eight said, “less than 1000 yen (about 7.7 euro). When asked to rank the items in preferential order, Prototype D (large scissors shape) was highest, followed by Prototype A (castanet shape), Prototype C (small scissors shape), and Prototype C (tongs shape). Regarding actual scenarios in which they would want to use the tools, the participants replied that they would like to use them when giving children cherry tomatoes at the table, preparing them for use in a salad while in the kitchen, and when eating bento, eating out, feeding a pet, and preparing a meal for a sick child in a care center. Lastly, when asked about the design of the tools and any points for improvement, the participants replied that it would be nice if the tools could also be used to mash food in addition to cutting and to slice cherry tomatoes into quarters. They also said that a carrying case would be desirable.

4 Discussion

To help solve health issues in the current era of advanced technology, we must make full use of methodologies from various fields; therefore, a living lab approach is crucial for achieving the goal of health for all. In the present study, we introduced Love & Safety Omura, a CBPR project employing a living lab approach, and discussed a community activity for choking prevention. A distinguishing feature of this project is that the Omura living lab has the ability to move freely from the micro level to the macro level and integrate these perspectives into innovations. As shown in Figure 5, social issues will not be solved without simultaneously dealing with the three dimensions, called the transformative dimensions; the societal dimension, the everyday life dimension, and the life elements dimension.

Figure 5: Transformative dimensions for social solution through innovations

In the societal dimension, we need to collect necessary data in order to reveal an accurate picture of social problems. To solve health-related problems, in particular, epidemiological understanding is necessary to assess a community's needs because the community's problems recognized by community members are not always reflected the real needs at a community level. Starting from co-design with a user does not always work to identify a community's real needs. Thus, we integrated the living lab approach into the CBPR approach to overcome this limitation. Once a target problem is identified in the societal dimension, we need to figure out why and how the problem occurs in the everyday life dimension and the life elements dimension using a living lab approach. For instance, to prevent injuries, it is important to understand how children interact with commercial products in the everyday life dimension and what characteristics of a product cause injuries in the life elements dimension. One's values, beliefs and attitudes toward practicing safe behaviors are also an important factor to understand in the life elements dimension. The transformative dimensions are also necessary for a project evaluation. A suggested safe behavior from the life element dimension needs to be exercised by people in the everyday life dimension. Effective behavior practices will be reflected by a reduction in injury occurrence in the societal dimension. In the field of living lab, their primary interest for most activities is to design, develop, and implement new technologies but is not always started with community problems at a macro level. We believe that CBPR and living labs are very good match, and integrating the perspectives of the transformative dimensions into a living lab will result in huge impacts on society.

The Omura living lab successfully established an ecosystem to handle all the dimensions together. We identified an important health problem based on localized data and concerns from community members, which promoted the sharing of invaluable knowledge for innovations. Product designers who were members of the Omura living lab shared knowledge for new designs and helped devise possible solutions for the problem. Community members' reflection data were collected to improve the design of prototypes while they received education regarding community health issues.

The benefits of applying the CBPR approach to a living lab approach are:

- Understanding true needs in a defined community based on data collected in the societal dimension. Epidemiological health data can be utilized to get a clear picture of health patterns and trends.
- Development of innovative solutions, which are relevant for community members.
- Increased likelihood of the adaptation of new solutions by community members.
- Establishment of a sustainable society that brings together people with different knowledge, skills and expertise, to solve social issues.
- People in a community will be fully empowered, which mean that new practices can be exercised after the intervention ended. These practices become a part of their lives.

However, this study did have some limitations. First, we believe that at least some of the community members should have been involved in the design process for *Hitokuchi* cut tools because in CBPR, the involvement of community members in all phases of the research

process is highly emphasized. Second, the number of participants in the focus group discussion was too small to provide adequate input in regard to improvements. Although we used injury data from different sources, including Omura injury surveillance data (Kitamura, 2010) and emergency transport records from a fire department, to identify community issues, we could have obtained much richer reflections of community needs in samples with more varied demographic characteristics. Third, *Hitokuchi* cut has not been made commercially available. We are currently working with potential companies interested in bringing these tools to market so that community members will be able to use them for injury prevention at home. Despite these limitations, the Love & Safety Omura project is an ideal ecosystem for improving childhood injury prevention strategies and can be applied to many global health issues.

5 Conclusion

In the present study, we investigated choking prevention in relation to the Love & Safety Omura project. In particular, we demonstrated how the dual SKC system worked to support the development of innovative prevention strategies applying a living lab and CBPR approach. Living lab approaches can help create innovative technology-based solutions for a variety of health issues, and represents the future direction of health-related research aimed at achieving sustainable development goals. The Omura approach has great potential to improve quality of life, particularly among children. In the future, we hope to expand the project activities and start a new project in different regions across Japan and in other countries.

References

- Ahmed, S., Swaine, B., Milot, M., Gaudet, C., Poldma, T., & Bartlett, G., et al. (2016). Creating an inclusive mall environment with the PREEDE-PROCEED model: a living lab case study. *Disability and Rehabilitation, 39*(21), 2198–2206. doi:10.1080/09638288.2016.1219401
- Brankaert, R., & den Ouden, E. (2017). The design-driven living lab: a new approach to exploring solutions to complex societal challenges. *Technology Innovation Management Review, 7*(1), 44–51.
- Calyam, P., Jahnke, I., Mishra, A., Antequera, R. B., Chemodanov, D., & Skubic, M. (2017). Toward an eldercare living lab for sensor-based health assessment. *IEEE Cloud Computing, 4*(3), 30–39.
- Chapin, M. M., Rochette, L. M., Annest, J. L., Haileyesus, T., Conner, K. A., & Smith, G. A. (2013). Nonfatal choking on food among children 14 years or younger in the United States, 2001–2009. *Pediatrics, 132*(2), 275–281.
- Coorevits, L., Coenen, T., Laureyssens, T., Schuurman, D., Van den Bosch, W., & De Marez, L. (2017). Living labs managing the intra-organizational knowledge exchange process when transitioning from closed to open innovation. *Open Living Lab Days Research Day Conference Proceedings 2017, 77–98*.
- Deguchi K., Oono, M., Kitamura, K., Nishida, Y. (2012). Childhood injury prevention through community-based participatory research – a multidimensional approach in the Love & Safety Omura study in Nagasaki, Japan – *Injury Prevention, 18*(S1), A108.
- Gregori, D. (2008). Preventing foreign body injuries in children: a key role to play for the injury community. *Injury Prevention, 14*(6), 411.
- (n.d.). Retrieved May 2, 2018, from <https://www.susysafe.org//index.php?lang=en>
- Israel, B. A., Schulz, A. J., Parker, E. A., & Backer, A. B. (2001). Community-based participatory research: policy recommendations for promoting a partnership approach in health research. *Education for Health, 14*(2), 182–197. doi:10.1080/13576280110051055
- Kitamura, K., Nishida, Y., Motomura, Y. (2010). Childhood injury modeling based on injury data collected using bodygraphic injury surveillance system. In Duffy, V. (Ed.), *Advances in Applied Digital Human Modeling*, (pp. 617-627). New York, NY: CRC Press.
- Leminen, S., Rajahonka, M., & Westerlund, M. (2017). Towards third-generation living lab networks in cities. *Innovation Management Review, 7*(11), 21–32.
- Gascó, M. (2017). *Living labs: implementing open innovation in the public sector. Government Information Quarterly, 34, 90–98*.
- Minkler, M. (2004). Ethical challenges for the “outside” researcher in community-based participatory research. *Health Education and Behavior, 31*(6), 684–697.
- Safe Kids Worldwide. (n.d.). Choking and strangulation. Retrieved May 2, 2018 from https://www.safekids.org/safetytips/field_risks/choking-and-strangulation
- Schuurman, D., & Tõnurist, P. (2017). Innovation in the public sector: exploring the characteristics and potential of living labs and innovation labs. *Technology Innovation*

Management Review, 7(1), 7–14.

Tokyo Fire Department. (n.d.). Nyuyouji no chissoku ya goin ni chui [Be careful of children's suffocation and choking]. Retrieved May 2, 2018 from <http://www.tfd.metro.tokyo.jp/lfe/topics/201304/tissoku/index.html>